

Environmental impact of newly designed surfactants with role in biofilm production

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Abstract

A continuous human population growth, industrialization and technical progress generate the need for new compounds design and synthesis. Development of new ecofriendly chemical compounds has been a priority for a sustainable and healthy environment, directly linked to the wellbeing of human society. The use of harmful chemical reagents and extensive energy consumption (obtained from pollution sources such as coal mining) during the chemical synthesis processes, most of the time, have had more negative impact on the environment than the final chemical product itself. Concepts such as green chemistry and circular economy became translated and applied to generate new compounds with high market value. Life cycle assessments (LCA) studies to assess the environmental impacts of new compounds help to enhance the energy efficiency and transitioning towards sustainable energy resources. Chemical compounds such as surfactants have been an important component of products compatible with domestic and industrial applications and subsequently they have been produced in large amounts having a wide range of chemical structures. Their mass production as became a burden to the environment, since a large amount of surfactants could end up into the environment, via domestic and industrial wastewaters. The benefits of their usage have been put in balance with their negative environmental impact as pollutants. In this respect, there is a need to develop new ecofriendly surfactants.

In this work, it was presented the chemical synthesis of oligomeric and polymeric thiophene-based surfactants. Their ecofriendly properties were tested point of view biodegradability and impact on a bacterial biological model. In addition, their whole chemical synthesis processes were analyzed through LCA studies. The new oligomeric and polymeric thiophene-based surfactants had a not significant environmental remanence and they have not exhibit important toxic effect on bacterial communities. Unfortunately, their chemical synthesis pathways have shown a potential larger negative effect on environmental and human health.

Keywords: *new designed surfactants, bacterial strains, growth inhibition, biodegradation potential, LCA*

1. Introduction

Surfactants or surface active agents are chemical compounds which lower the surface tension by their tendency to get adsorbed at surfaces and interfaces. They possess dual characteristics based on their hydrophilic and hydrophobic chemical structures and could be classified into four different categories such as anionic, cationic, nonionic, and zwitterionic (Zhu and Free, 2022). Surfactants are involved in two main phenomena, adsorption and aggregation (e.g., micelles and other aggregated structures) and, therefore, they have been an important chemical source for industrial and domestic applications.

Surfactants are widely used as household cleaning and personal care products and have industrial applications such as i) the food industry as emulsifiers, ii) agriculture as additives to pesticides and herbicides to enhance the adhesion to plant surfaces, iii) the oil and gas industry to enhance oil recovery; iv) the textile industry for dyeing and printing or v) the wastewater treatment (Farias et al., 2021; Massarweh and Abushaikka, 2020; Schramm, 2005). Unfortunately, the economic success of using surfactants in various applications has been counterbalanced by their environment presence as pollutants, especially in large urban areas (Braga & Varesche, 2014). There are three major methods for removing surfactants from wastewater, mainly by domestic and industrial wastewater treatment plants (WWTP), through: i) physical methods (precipitation, adsorption, flocculation, electrolysis, and sonication); ii) chemical methods (oxidation with oxygen, ozone, H₂O₂/UV) and iii) biological treatments (aerobic and anaerobic degradation).

The biological treatments (biodegradation) are carried out by anaerobic and aerobic bacterial communities from the WWTPs-activated sludge which generate a low-cost and effective pollutant removal alternative to the physical and chemical methods (Wu Q. et al, 2019). In spite of this, surfactants were not largely removed by WWTP, because surfactants presence in industrial or domestic wastewaters could impair the regular WWTP functionality. Surfactants could break down microbial communities' viability, decreasing the activated sludge production or pollutants biodegradation efficiency which could lead to WWTP operational issues. In addition, surfactants could enhance the wastewater foamability which also could generate WWTP operational issues by increasing the risk of overflow to WWTP surrounding environment.

Surfactants reaching freshwater systems often can also cause severe modification to aquatic biota by i) inducing alterations in oxidative stress parameters (Arora et al., 2022; Gheorghe et al., 2022; Bhattacharya et al. 2021; Sobrino-Figueroa, 2018), ii) bioaccumulation in primary producers like algae to consumers (crustaceans) (Kaczerewska et al. 2020; Renaud et al, 2014) or iii) endocrine disruptors in vertebrates (fish) (Sobrino-Figueroa, 2018). In certain cases, the biotransformation products could be more toxic than the parent compounds (Chiriac et al., 2023a, 2023b; Jurado et al., 2009). At the molecular level, several surfactants, such as the anionic ones, could bind to peptides, enzymes or DNA, causing abnormal folding of polypeptide chains or changing the surface charge of molecules, and subsequently could alter biological functions (Ivanković & Hrenović, 2010). An alternative to biological degradation of surfactants, there are physico-chemical methods to induce pollutant degradability, but they are quite expensive. The reagents used for surfactants chemical oxidation can generate final degraded products with greater toxicity compared to the primary pollutant's compounds. Overall, physico-chemical methods become less appealing than the biological treatments which generate a low-cost and effective pollutant removal biotechnology (Paun et al. 2021; Wu Q. et al, 2019). There are many biological models to analyze pollutants' ecotoxicity such as freshwater fish, aquatic and terrestrial plants or benthic and planktonic crustaceans, but the European chemicals safety guidelines promoted the reduction of animal (especially vertebrate) testing by introducing the mandatory data sharing requirement and by encouraging the use of alternative testing methods such as cells (Gheorghe et al., 2016; Szklarek, et al, 2015). There are international norms/guidelines and requirements such as Regulation (EC) No 648/2004, where it was established a common rule to enable detergents and surfactants to be sold and used across the EU, while, at the same time, providing a high degree of protection to the environment and human health. Regulation (EC) no. 66/2010 for EU Ecolabel established the ecolabel criteria for the product with a reduced environmental impact during their life cycle based on relevant scientific information (especially biodegradability and toxicity).

In addition to the environmental impact induced by chemical compounds such as oligomeric and polymeric surfactants, their entire synthesis process as well as their use and disposal show be monitored in respect to human and environmental health. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a useful tool to evaluate the environmental impacts associated with all life stages of a product, from raw material extraction

through production, use and disposal (Cucurachi et al., 2018; Guinée et al., 2018). It can help technology developers and industries identify opportunities for reducing environmental impacts and improving sustainability. In the field of chemical synthesis, LCA allows researchers and manufacturers to assess the environmental impacts of various chemical processes and reactions, such as carbon footprint, energy consumption, emissions, and resource depletion at each stage of the synthesis (Parvatker and Eckelman, 2019; Piccinno et al., 2016). In addition, LCA enables chemists to compare different synthesis pathways and select the most sustainable options. This is crucial for developing greener and more sustainable chemical processes, which could optimize resource use and minimize waste (Bennett et al., 2019; Piccinno et al., 2016).

In this work, the chemical synthesis process of new thiophene based surfactants with potential application in electron transfer for biomimetic devices and sensors was analyzed based on life cycle assessment (LCA) criteria. In addition, thiophene based surfactants biodegradability and ecofriendly potentials were analyzed by bacterial strains as biological models.

Biological models, especially bacteria cells, have a special significance due to their robust adaptability to toxic compounds and their global environmental presence. Bacteria have a simple structure and therefore they are easy to be used in evaluation studies, providing significant and quick information about potential toxic effects of chemical compounds on the environment. Bacteria provide a rapid detection at a molecular level of which biological effects were induced by a specific chemical pollutant compound. Moreover, a bacterial community could react to a potential harmful pollutant by changing their populational community structure, which make them non-specific environmental "sensors" to stress. Therefore, bacterial monitoring are easier to use, economical and reproducible alternative to ecotoxicity tests for establishing the harmful effects of chemicals / contaminated environmental samples on small organisms (invertebrates, algae, ciliates, rotifers, plants and bacteria (Stoica et al, 2014).

In this context, the need for an early detection of unexpected changes occurring in the environment requires the use of indicators capable of reacting sensitively to changes in the environment. The oligomeric and polymeric surfactants based on thiophene compounds showed a significant biodegradability potential in presence of microbial communities isolated from a fully functional municipal WWTP. Their biodegradability potential matched the ecofriendly properties in case of reaching the environment therefore biomimetic devices and sensors based on these chemical compounds could have a very low environmental impact.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Reactions needing an inert atmosphere were performed under argon using oven-dried glassware and Schlenk techniques. All anhydrous solvents and reagents were obtained from commercial suppliers and used as received without further purifications: 2-bromo-3-hexyl-5-iodothiophene (Fluorochem, 95%), isopropylmagnesium chloride solution (Merck) and [1,3-bis(diphenylphosphine)propane]-nickel(II) dichloride (TCI, 98%).

Tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) catalysts were prepared according to a procedure described by Coulson et al., 1972, Kong et al., 2009 and Lee et al., 2011. TLC were carried out on Merck DC Kieselgel 60 F-254 aluminium sheets and spots were visualized with UV-lamp ($\lambda = 254/365$ nm) if necessary. Preparative purifications were performed by silica gel column chromatography (Merck 40–60 μ M) and flash chromatography was carried out using Biotage® Isolera™ Systems (UV-Vis 200 nm – 800 nm detector) over silica cartridges (Sfär HC D).

2.2. Characterization methods

NMR spectroscopy and MS spectrometry were performed at the Laboratoire de Mesures Physiques (LMP) of the University of Montpellier (UM). ^1H and $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 400 MHz Avance III HD and 500 MHz Avance III spectrometers at 298 K. CDCl_3 (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.8%) was used as received. ^1H and $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectra were calibrated using the relative chemical shift of the residual non-deuterated solvent as an internal standard. Chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm. Abbreviations used for NMR spectra are as follows: s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; m, multiplet. High-resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were recorded on a Bruker MicroTof QII instrument in positive/negative modes (ESI). Number-averaged (M_n) and weight-averaged (M_w) molecular weights and the molecular weight distribution (Đ) of **P3HT-block-P3TEGT** and **P3HT-ran-P3TEGT** were measured using size exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a Polymer Laboratories liquid chromatograph equipped with a PL-DG802 degasser, an isocratic HPLC pump LC 1120 (flow rate of 1 mL min^{-1}), a Marathon autosampler (loop volume of 200 μL , solution concentration of 1 mg mL^{-1}), a PL-DRI refractive index detector, and three columns: a PL gel 10 mm guard column and two PL gel Mixed-B 10 mm columns (linear columns for the separation of molecular weight polystyrene standards ranging from 500 to 10^6 Da). The eluent used was THF at a flow rate of 1 mL min^{-1} at 35°C . Polystyrene standards were used to calibrate the SEC.

2.3. Synthesis of oligomeric and polymeric surfactants

3DT-3TEGT. Under argon, 3-dodecyl-2-(4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)thiophene (**1**) (1.066 mmol) and 2,5-dibromo-3-(2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)methylthiophene (**2**) (0.216 g, 0.520 mmol) were placed into a two-necked 100 mL round-bottom flask with anhydrous THF (12 mL). 4 mL of a 2 M sodium carbonate aqueous solution was then added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 minutes. After addition of tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) catalyst (0.018 g, 0.016 mmol), the mixture was refluxed for 24 hours. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction was quenched with water (20 mL). The organic phase was then extracted with dichloromethane (3 x 50 mL), dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 , filtered and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was then purified by column chromatography on silica gel using a mixture of hexane and ethyl acetate (7/3, v/v) as an eluent leading to **3DT-3TEGT** as a yellow oil (0.21 g, 52%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ = 7.32 (d, 1H, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$), 7.18 (s, 1H), 7.15 (d, 1H, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$), 6.96 (d, 1H, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$), 6.92 (d, 1H, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$), 4.42 (s, 2H), 3.64-3.36 (m, 18H), 2.77 (t, 2H, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 7.8 \text{ Hz}$), 2.55 (t, 2H, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 7.8 \text{ Hz}$), 1.63-1.24 (m, 41H), 0.85 (m, 6H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 142.9, 139.8, 138.4, 136.7, 131.6, 130.5, 130.2, 129.0, 127.4, 127.1, 125.9, 123.8, 72.0, 70.8, 70.70, 69.5, 66.9, 59.2, 32.0, 31.0, 30.8, 29.8, 29.7, 29.6, 29.5, 29.0, 22.8, 14.2. HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{76}\text{NO}_4\text{S}_3$ [$\text{M} + \text{NH}_4$] $^+$ 778.4931 Da, found: 778.4932 Da.

P3HT-block-P3TEGT. In two two-neck round bottom flasks (100 mL) equipped with a magnetic bar, 2-bromo-3-hexyl-5-iodothiophene (**3**) (0.558 g, 1.50 mmol) and **2** (0.21 g, 0.5 mmol) were dried under vacuum after heating at 50°C (magnetic heating stirrer) during 10 minutes and then, cooled at room temperature. Anhydrous THF (10 mL) was then added for each flask by using a cannula and then, the solutions were stirred at 0°C for 15 minutes. Isopropylmagnesium chloride (2.0 M in THF) (0.75 mL and 0.25 mL) was then transferred to respectively, **3** and **2**-containing flask using syringe after which the mixtures were stirred at 0°C for 1h. $\text{NiCl}_2(\text{dppp})$ (18 mg, 0.03 mmol) was then added to the solution containing **2** after warming the solution at room temperature. The solution containing **2** and catalyst was then stirred for 2h before the addition of solution containing **3**. The resulting mixture was then left under stirring overnight. The reaction was finally quenched by the addition of MeOH followed by precipitation in MeOH (200 mL) and filtration. The resulting polymer was then purified by Soxhlet extraction in methanol/acetone/hexane and chloroform (24h each time, 300 mL solvent, balloon heater). The chloroform solution was then concentrated (from 300 to 30 mL) and methanol (300 mL) was added to precipitate the polymer. The polymer was isolated by filtration (0.20 g, 54%). SEC (THF, PS standards): M_w

= 3 500 g mol⁻¹, M_n = 3 000 g mol⁻¹, Đ = 1.15. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 6.98 (s, ArH, 1H), 4.68 (s, -CH₂-O), 3.78-3.48 (m, -CH₂-O), 3.35 (s, -OCH₃ (P3TEGT)), 2.82-2.39 (m, -CH₂ (P3HT)), 1.72-1.28 (m, -CH₂-), 0.91 (s, -CH₃ (P3HT), 3H) ppm.

P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT. In two two-neck round bottom flasks (100 mL) equipped with a magnetic bar, **3** (0.58 g, 1.55 mmol) and **2** (0.62 g, 1.48 mmol) were dried under vacuum after heating at 50°C (magnetic heating stirrer) during 10 minutes and then, cooled at room temperature. Anhydrous THF (10 mL) was then added for each flask by using a cannula and then, the solutions were stirred at 0°C for 15 minutes. Isopropylmagnesium chloride (2.0 M in THF) (0.77 mL and 0.74 mL) was then transferred to respectively, **3**- and **2**-containing flask using syringe after which the mixtures were stirred at 0°C for 1h. NiCl₂(dppp) (48 mg, 0.09 mmol) was then added to the solution containing **3** followed by the solution containing **2**. The mixture was then stirred overnight. The reaction was finally quenched by the addition of MeOH followed by precipitation in MeOH (200 mL) and filtration. The resulting polymer was then purified by Soxhlet extraction in methanol/acetone/hexane and chloroform (24h each time, 300 mL solvent, balloon heater). The chloroform solution was then concentrated (from 300 to 30 mL) and methanol (300 mL) was added to precipitate the polymer. The polymer was isolated by filtration (0.35 mg, 52%). SEC (THF, PS standards): M_w = 3 900 g mol⁻¹, M_n = 2 600 g mol⁻¹, Đ = 1.49. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 6.99 (s, ArH, 1H), 4.64 (s, -CH₂-O), 3.76-3.62 (m, -CH₂-O), 3.53 (m, -CH₂-O), 3.34 (s, -OCH₃ (P3TEGT)), 2.78-2.36 (m, -CH₂ (P3HT)), 1.69-1.28 (m, -CH₂-), 0.91 (s, -CH₃ (P3HT), 3H) ppm.

2.4. Biodegradation of oligomeric and polymeric surfactants

The biodegradation potential of oligomeric and polymeric surfactants (3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT) was analyzed based on biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅) (ISO 5815-1 method) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) (ISO 6060 method) ratio, namely Biodegradability Index (Table 1). The BOD₅/COD ratio of ≥ 0.5, the tested substance could be biologically oxidized and is highly biodegradable in the environment. BOD₅/COD ratio between 0.2-0.5 shows that the tested substance has medium biodegradation potential in the environment, while a ratio of <0.2 BOD₅/COD suggests that the compounds are non-biodegradable (Rudaru et al., 2022).

Table 1. The Biodegradability index

BOD/COD ratio	
<0.2	non-biodegradable
0.2-0.5	medium biodegradable
>0.5	highly biodegradable

Respiration tests were performed by incubating a bacterial consortium isolated from a municipal WWTP activated sludge in presence of oligomeric and polymeric surfactants according to EN ISO 8192 standard method (similar with the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) guideline no.209). Briefly, a bacterial consortium was incubated in presence of 100 mg/L oligomeric and polymeric surfactants at a constant temperature of 20°C±2°C up to 1h. The oxygen consumption (respiration rate) of each test was measured with an oxygen-sensitive electrode system (Orion Star A329, Thermo Scientific, Germany) every 15 minutes.

2.5. Bacterial growth inhibition tests

Two non-pathogenic Gram-negative bacterial strains *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) (NCTC 12241) (National Collection of Type Cultures, UK) and *Pseudomonas putida* (*P. putida*) (ATCC 17514) (American Type Culture Collection, USA) and one non-pathogenic Gram-positive bacteria strain *Lactobacillus acidophilus* (*L.*

acidophilus) (ATCC 4356) (American Type Culture Collection, USA). Bacterial strains *L. acidophilus*, cultured on MRS broth (VWR Chemicals, Belgium), *E. coli* and *P. putida*, cultured on Lauryl tryptose broth (Scharlau, Spain) were incubated in absence or presence of oligomeric and polymeric surfactants at 37°C for 24h under gentle rotation at 130 rpm (New Brunswick Scientific, Innova 44). The effect of these compounds on bacterial growth was spectrophotometrically monitored at wavelength of 600 nm (OD_{600nm}), using a UV-VIS spectrometer (VWR International, USA).

2.6. Non-ionic surfactants detection

The concentration of nonionic surfactants was determined by UV spectrophotometric measurement. Briefly, surfactants were mixed with Dragendorff reagent and the formed Bismuth-surfactants pellet was solubilized with ammonium tartrate. The concentration of Bismuth, directly equivalent to the concentration of the surface agent, was optically measured at 263.5nm on a spectrophotometer Shimadzu (Shimadzu, Japan). The calibration curve was made using Triton-X (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) as certified material.

2.7 Life Cycle Assessment

A life cycle assessment (LCA) of the environmental impacts was conducted on 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT, and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT newly synthesized molecules, respectively. The system boundary of the life cycle assessment of the environmental impacts of oligomeric and polymeric surfactant (3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT, and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT) molecules was defined as cradle-to-gate of 1 gram of oligomeric and polymeric surfactants molecules synthesized in European regions.

The LCA software used was Activity Browser, and the database utilized was ecoinvent 3.9, with the EF family method applied for the environmental impact assessment. Life cycle inventory (LCI) data was obtained from the laboratory within the Department of Chemistry at the University of Montpellier according to a flowchart depicting the whole synthesis process for the targeted oligomeric and polymeric surfactants (Figure 1). The material consumption of various related chemicals was recorded. Chemical stoichiometry methods to derive the target chemicals and calculate their environmental impacts were performed on chemicals not shown in the ecoinvent database, but involved in chemical synthesis process

Figure 1. Onsite life cycle inventory data collection process at ICGM, using 3DT-3TEGT as an example.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Synthesis of thiophene-based surfactants.

We developed a series of amphiphilic thiophene-based oligomers and polymers (**3DT-3TEGT** vs. **P3HT-block-P3TEGT** and **P3HT-ran-P3TEGT**), linked in an α,ω (1,4)-pattern to maintain conjugation and preserve their optoelectronic properties (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Structure of thiophene-based surfactants.

The selection of the thiophene platform was driven by its status as a benchmark material for optoelectronic applications, owing to its tunable optical and electronic properties, which can be readily adjusted through well-established synthetic techniques (Mishra et al. 2009). The ability of amphiphilic oligothiophenes and polythiophenes to self-assemble in water into a wide range of structures such as spheres, elongated micelles, bilayer structures, core-shell discs or cylinders in solution depending on the conjugation length, the architecture (block or graft copolymers) or the nature of polar headgroup (cationic, nonionic ethylene oxide, peptide) (Rijn et al., 2011; Thomas et al., 2014; Reitzel et al., 2000; Brustolin et al., 2002; Winchell et al., 2023; Mohamed et al., 2014; Janeliunas et al., 2013; Houston et al., 2017). Following this strategy, we developed a series of amphiphilic thiophene-based oligomers and polymers which incorporate hydrophobic alkyl chains and nonionic ethylene glycol hydrophilic chains and with different conjugation length (number of thiophene units). The polar ethylene glycol group was selected for its better solubility in organic solvents compared to ionic groups, simplifying the purification process. Random and block copolymers were also prepared allowing to examine the effect of conjugation length. Random copolymers are easier to synthesize than block or graft copolymers and allow for a broader selection of monomers (Ding and Olesik, 2003, Deniz et al., 2005). Studies highlight their advantages, including cost-effectiveness and simpler characterization (Yan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2010; Yamamoto and Morishima, 1999).

3DT-3TEGT was prepared by a palladium-catalyzed Suzuki cross-coupling reaction of hydrophobic and hydrophilic thiophene building blocks (Figure 3A) and isolated in 52% yield. Its structure was confirmed by combining NMR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry (Figure S1-3 in the Supporting Information). Notably, high-resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrometry (positive mode) confirmed the presence of pseudo-

molecular ion $[M + NH_4]^+$ at $m/z = 778.4932$ Da (calcd $m/z = 778.4931$ Da) (Figure S4 in the Supporting Information). Random **P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT** and block **P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT** copolymers were synthesized by using Kumada–Tamao catalyst-transfer condensation polymerization (CTCP). However, **P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT** was prepared by the sequential addition of the activated 2-bromo-3-hexyl-5-iodothiophene and 2,5-dibromo-3-(2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)methylthiophene monomers to a nickel catalyst (Figure 3B) while for **P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT**, the two monomers were added simultaneously (Figure 3C). The compositions of the two copolymers were determined by 1H NMR spectroscopy based on the characteristic peaks of P3HT ($\delta = 0.5$ – 2.8 ppm) and P3TEGT ($\delta = 3.2$ – 4.8 ppm) (Lee et al. 2019). The weight fractions of P3HT were estimated to be 81% and 55% in **P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT** and **P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT**.

Figure 3. Synthetic pathway towards thiophene-based oligomeric and polymeric surfactants

To determine the critical micelle concentration (CMC) of the amphiphilic terthiophenes, scattered light intensity was measured as a function of concentration. The results were visualized by plotting scattered light intensity against concentration, revealing a sharp increase at the CMC. This method relies on the principle that larger particles scatter light more effectively than small molecules. Solutions of the synthesized surfactants were prepared at varying concentrations, and the CMC values were determined using dynamic light scattering (DLS). The copolymers **P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT** and **P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT** display significantly lower CMC values, approximately 0.05 mM and 0.002 mM, respectively, compared to **3HT-3TEGT** (0.13 mM). This difference can be attributed to the larger number of hydrophobic thiophene units (around 15) in the copolymers, compared to only 3 units in **3HT-3TEGT**. Between the random and block copolymers, the higher CMC observed for **P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT** is due to the greater proportion of the hydrophilic P3TEGT fraction in comparison to **P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT**.

3.2. Biodegradability potential of surfactant compounds

Surfactants could be resilient to biodegradation and they could impact on WWTP efficacy by disrupting the microbial community involved in biological pollution treatment. In most of the cases, bacterial communities, involved in pollutants biodegradation, adapt to various chemical composition from wastewater (Nita-Lazar et al., 2016a, 2016b), but in certain cases microbial biodegradation activity was disrupted by the surfactants present in wastewaters (Zhang et al., 2011). The BOD₅/COD ratio (biodegradability index) has been generally considered the „cut-off point” between biodegradable and non-biodegradable compounds, potential pollutants.

The BOD₅ and COD assays on surfactant compounds showed medium biodegradability potential of 3DT-3TEGT compound, but highly biodegradation potential for P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compounds (Table 2). A BOD₅/COD ratio higher than 0.5 is an indication for a compound with a high biodegradable potential (Table 1).

Table 2. COD and BOD₅ values of 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compounds

Compounds/parameters	COD	BOD ₅	BOD ₅ /COD
	mg O ₂ /L	mg O ₂ /L	
3DT-3TEGT	2049	717	0.35
P3HT-<i>block</i>-P3TEGT	2091	1505	0.72
P3HT-<i>ran</i>-P3TEGT	2003	1121	0.56

The biodegradation potential of these surfactants and their potential impact on the environment were correlated with the microbial respiration rate in presence of each surfactant compound. The microbial respiration rate gives an indication of surfactants biodegradability. A reduced respiration rate is an indicator of a potential chemical compounds toxic effect on bacterial communities from the activated sludge.

This method gives information on inhibitory or stimulatory effects after a short exposure time (usually 30 min up to 180 min or even more) of the tested material (surfactant compounds) on microorganisms/bacteria from activated sludge. An activated sludge collected from a municipal WWTP was incubated up to 1h in presence of 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compounds. Overall oxygen uptake was higher when activate sludge was incubated in presence of surfactants compared to control, activated sludge incubated without surfactants (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The effect of surfactants 3DT-3TEGT (blue line), P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT (orange line) and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT (grey line) compounds on microbial oxygen uptake. All studies represent one of two independent experiments.

The activated sludge incubated in presence of 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT or P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT increased the oxygen consumption compared to control (activated sludge incubated without surfactants). The P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT had the highest oxygen consumption rate up to 45 min when less than 10% dissolved oxygen remained compared to control. The P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compound induced an oxygen consumption at lower rate than P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT up to 45 min, but reached the oxygen remaining level of P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT after 60 min. This could be explained by some chemical structures from P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT which were initially more difficult to be biodegraded, however after a certain point all chemical compounds were biodegraded at the same level as P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT (Figure 4). Overall, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compounds seemed to be easily biodegraded by a bacterial community from an activated sludge collected from a municipal WWTP.

The 3DT-3TEGT compound was also biodegraded by the bacterial community, but at a lower rate compared to P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compounds, based on oxygen consumption rate. The oxygen consumption rate induced by 3DT-3TEGT seemed to be increased after 45 min, which could be explained by reaching a biodegraded 3DT-3TEGT compound which could be easily microbiological further processed.

The oxygen consumption rate was correlated with the amount of surfactants, up to 60 min. The surfactant quantification after 1h incubation with activated sludge showed a limited degradation for 3DT-3TEGT and more than 50% degradation for P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT and up to 70% degradation for P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT (Figure 5).

Figure 5. 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT surfactant quantification

P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compounds were properly correlated to activated sludge respiration rate. The 3DT-3TEGT quantification during 60 min matched the respiration rate (oxygen consumption) generated by the microbial communities from the activated sludge, too.

The bithiophene is the main structure of P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compounds and the terthiophene with an ethoxylated chain were the main component of 3DT-3TEGT. Aromatic rings are more difficult to biodegrade than acyclic hydrocarbons (Kuenemann et al., 1990) and the number of rings plays an important role in biodegradability, as well as the length of the alkyl chain trigger the increase of surfactants toxicity (Ivanković and Hrencović, 2010). Terthiophene contains three aromatic rings compared to bithiophene which could explain the low biodegradability rate of compound 3DT-3TEGT compared to compounds P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT. The alcohol ethoxylates structures, RO(CH₂CH₂O)_nH - a linear alcohol ethoxylates-, have been often utilized in home applications and therefore, they have been investigated in biodegradability tests (Evans et al, 1997).

The oxygen uptake was a measure of the ecotoxicological effect of surfactant compounds on bacterial metabolism potential to biodegrade 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT, P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT surfactant compounds. A higher oxygen uptake rate meant an active bacterial metabolism involved in surfactant biodegradation. Overall, it appeared that these compounds did not exhibit any toxic effects on bacterial communities found in activated sludge from WWTP. Moreover, the surfactant compounds could be biodegraded during the standard treatment steps during a WWTP process, without having the necessity of adding specific bacterial strains to boost their biodegradation.

3.3. Bacterial growth inhibition

The potential toxic effect of newly designed and synthesized surfactant compounds (Figure 6) was analyzed by testing the bacterial growth inhibition on non-pathogenic bacterial models, such as Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. Two Gram negative bacterial strains (*E. coli* and *P. putida*) and one Gram positive bacterial strain (*L. acidophilus*) were incubated in presence of the three surfactants (3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT, and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT). The effect of surfactants on all three bacterial strains was examined by bacterial growth rate and viability. All three bacterial strains were robustly grown in their specific growth medium and the ecotoxicity tests could be performed by incubating bacteria in

presence of various concentrations of surfactants class electronic molecules (3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT, P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT).

Results showed that at shorter incubation times, up to 2h, a slight bacterial growth inhibition occurred, while on a longer incubation times up to 24h the normal bacterial growth resumed, perhaps due to bacterial adaptation mechanisms to surfactants toxic effect. The bacterial growth rate matched the control sample, bacteria incubation without 100 mg/L 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT, P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT, for a longer incubation times (Figure 6). This effect could be observed for all bacterial strains, whether Gram positive or Gram negative, incubated in presence of 100 mg/L 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT, P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT. The effect specificity between compounds and bacterial strains could be better observed at short incubation time (2h).

Figure 6. Bacterial growth in presence of 100 mg/L 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT compounds. a) *Lactobacillus acidophilus*; b) *Escherichia coli*; c) *Pseudomonas putida*. All studies represent one of three independent experiments.

The 3DT-3TEGT compound seemed to have a specific effect on Gram-positive *L. acidophilus* strain especially at shorter incubation time (2h) when the bacteria growth inhibition reached up to 50%. At 24h incubation *L. acidophilus* growth rate recovered (less than 10% inhibition) compared to control samples. 3DT-3TEGT compound had an effect on *L. acidophilus*, but limited one on the other two bacterial strains. However, Zhao et al. (2015) reported specific growth inhibition of Gram positive *Staphylococcus aureus* in presence of oligo (thiophene ethynylene) compound at 180 ng/mL during 30 min incubation time, rather than longer incubation time (60 min). On the opposite side, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT compound seemed to affect more at short and long incubation times the Gram-negative strains (*E. coli* and *P. putida*) compared to Gram-positive strain. In addition, it showed a specific persistent toxic effect on *E. coli* for longer incubation time (24h) compared to *P. putida* which recovered after 2h in incubation. P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT induced a not significant growth rate inhibition to *P. putida*, but generated a similar growth inhibition pattern, a lower toxic effect for longer incubation times, for *E. coli* and *L. acidophilus* (Figure 6). The toxicity effect of various surfactants on *P. putida* growth revealed that Gram negative bacteria has lower sensitivity compared to marine microalgae *P. tricornutum* as previously reported Rios et al. (2023). Sutormin et al. (2023) observed that the aggregation of the surfactant molecules into micelles could cause oxygen diffusion limitation which in turn has a negative effect on Gram negative bioluminescent bacterium *Photobacterium phosphoreum*. Overall, the ecotoxicity tests on specific biological models, revealed that 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT, P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT, surfactant compounds had not a significant influence for longer incubation times on Gram positive and Gram negative bacterial strains.

3.4 Life Cycle Assessment

LCA data collection was obtained from lab researchers directly involved in oligomeric and polymeric surfactants syntheses and experts from the host institute. Collected data was then used for Life cycle inventory (LCI) and relevant data can be found in Tables S1 and S2 of Supporting Information.

A contribution analysis to identify key contributors or stages with high environmental impacts, followed by recommendations for syntheses process improvements, was conducted based on LCA results.

LCA results pointed out that 3DT-3TEGT exhibits significantly lower overall environmental impact compared to P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT (Figure 7). This disparity could be attributed to the use of organic solvents for synthesizing P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT, as well as the overall efficiency of the synthesis process, the choice of catalysts, and the properties of the final products. For instance, P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT require extensive use of organic solvents in their production (i.e., large amounts of Chloroform and other organic solvents such as Methanol, Acetone, Hexane, in the quenching and purification stage), which raises both energy demands and complexity in waste management, thereby increasing potential risks to ecosystems. In addition, P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT performs better than P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT in each category due to less use of chemicals, such as M1, 1,3-bis(diphenylphosphino)propane]-nickel(II) dichloride, etc. For 3DT-3TEGT, the choice of palladium as a catalyst for 3DT-3TEGT, while enhancing reaction selectivity and conversion rates, simultaneously increases the environmental burden associated with the consumption of metals.

In terms of climate change impact, approximately 25%-30% of the contribution from P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT stems from the use of trichloromethane. This proves the severe effects of the use of organic solvents. Besides, around 20% is from high-voltage electricity, and over 10% is the heat from natural gas. Furthermore, 3DT-3TEGT shows that around 30% of the impact of electricity reflects the industrial process's reliance on energy. This also stresses the importance of evaluating the environmental friendliness of electricity sources. Therefore, transitioning to cleaner energy sources in operations is recommended to mitigate environmental impacts further. Regarding the eutrophication impacts (freshwater) of all molecules, the 30% contribution from spoilage related to hard coal mining indicates that the environmental impacts associated with coal extraction and management are significant. The mining and disposal of hard coal can lead to contamination of soil and water, alongside detrimental effects on surrounding ecosystems. It is worth noting that for 3DT-3TEGT, the impact of the use of ethanol (from ethylene) contributed to around 40% of eutrophication.

Figure 7. Characterization results of 3DT-3TEGT, P3HT-BLOCK-P3TEGT and P3HT-RAN-P3TEGT based on the LCA results.

In terms of ecotoxicity (freshwater), the significant contributions (over 40%) are from water discharges related to petroleum and natural gas extraction, highlighting a crucial need for improvements in water management and discharge strategies in the industries. Lastly, regarding human toxicity (carcinogenic), the prominent source of carcinogenic risks for P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT is trichloromethane, which contributes to over 80% of the impacts. This point emphasizes the potential risks

of using trichloromethane in the chemical synthesis process and industrial applications to mitigate potential health hazards. Furthermore, investing in research for alternatives or reduction in the use of organic solvents and other harmful chemical substances is encouraged to advance the principles of green chemistry. Additionally, a solvent recovery strategy can enhance the sustainability of future synthesis processes by promoting the circular economy and enabling the reuse of materials.

4. Conclusions

Oligomeric and polymeric thiophene-based surfactants (P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT) had a high biodegradation potential calculated by BOD₅/COD and it was confirmed by respirometry tests.

Chemical composition of oligomeric and polymeric thiophene-based surfactants modulated their biodegradability potential inducing a specific effect on Gram-positive vs Gram-negative. The terthiophene chemical structure from 3DT-3TEGT composition had a decreased biodegradation potential compared to bithiophene chemical structure from P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT. Terthiophene surfactant, composed of two different thiophenes building blocks - one bearing a hydrophobic dodecyl alkyl chain group (apolar group) and another one a hydrophylic non-ionic ethylene-glycol one (polar group) -, seemed to affect only Gram-positive bacterial strains, lacking an extra outer membrane, compared to Gram-negative strains.

The ecotoxicological studies on longer incubation times, performed on Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria, showed that newly designed and synthesized oligomeric and polymeric thiophene-based surfactants seemed no to have a potential toxic effect on the environment. In addition, these surfactants seemed to be ecofriendly with the environment by having a high biodegradable potential, and subsequently they persistence into the environment could be very short, decreasing the potential of bioaccumulation.

Unfortunately, the chemical synthesis processes of these compounds had a more harmful potential than oligomeric and polymeric thiophene-based surfactants themselves. The environmental impact of P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT synthesis process was higher than 3DT-3TEGT synthesis process due to an extensive use of organic solvents such as chloroform, methanol, hexane, etc. In addition, the use of trichloromethane, especially during P3HT-*ran*-P3TEGT and P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT synthesis process could enhance the climate change impact on the environment. Climate change could be also enhanced by producing electricity, needed during the chemicals syntheses of surfactants, from environmental friendly sources, not coal mining. Coal mining and climate change could together impact on environment (eutrophication and pollution) and human health.

Overall, it is important to develop syntheses of new chemical compounds with ecofriendly applications together with a whole chemical synthesis processes based on circular economy and green chemistry.

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Figure S1. ¹H NMR spectrum of 3HT-3TEGT (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) at 298K.

Figure S2. ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectrum of 3HT-3TEGT (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) at 298K.

Figure S3. High-Resolution ESI-TOF (positive mode) mass spectrum of **3HT-3TEGT**.

Figure S4. ¹H NMR spectrum of **P3HT-block-P3TEGT** (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) at 298K.

Figure S5. SEC profiles obtained during the synthesis of the **P3HT-*block*-P3TEGT** copolymer in THF.

Figure S6. ¹H NMR spectrum of **P3HT-ran-P3TEGT** (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) at 298k.

Figure S7. SEC profile of the **P3HT-ran-P3TEGT** copolymer in THF.

Figure S8. Plot of the intensity of scattered light (in kilo counts per second) obtained for various concentrations of **3HT-3TEGT** prepared in deionized water. The intersection of the two lines in the intensity data corresponds to the critical micelle concentration.

Figure S9. Plot of the intensity of scattered light (in kilo counts per second) obtained for various concentrations of **P3HT-block-P3TEGT** prepared in deionized water.

Figure S10. Plot of the intensity of scattered light (in kilo counts per second) obtained for various concentrations of **P3HT-ran-P3TEGT** prepared in deionized water.

Table S1. Life cycle inventory (LCI) for 3DT-3TEGT

Synthesis step	Unit operation	Chemicals	Unit	Amount	Time [min]	Condition	Energy [kWh]	Device	Yield	Other
1. Synthesis of 2-bromo-3-dodecylthiophene (a) C ₁₆ H ₂₇ BrS										
1.1	Dissolution	Dodecyl thiophene	g	3				Beaker		
		Glacial acetic acid	mL	50						
1.2	Heating	Recrystallized N-Bromosuccinimide, NBS	g	2.4	30	45 °C		Heating Plate		
1.3	Extraction	H ₂ O	mL	100						
		ether	mL	100						
1.4	Washing	NaOH	M	2		3 times				
		H ₂ O	mL	100		3 times				
1.5	Drying	Anhydrous magnesium sulfate (MgSO ₄)	g	2						
1.6	Purification	Hexane:Ethyl acetate	L	1L:0.2L				160 °C, 0.1 mbar	0.66	
2. Synthesis of 2-(3-dodecylthiophen-2-yl)-4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolane (b) C ₂₂ H ₃₉ BO ₂ S										
2.1	Reflux	2-bromo-3-Dodecyl Thiophene (compound a)	g	2				Heating plate		
		Potassium Acetate	g	1.78						
		Bis(pinacolato)diboron	g	2.3						
		Palladium Catalyst (PdCl ₂ (dPPf) ₂)	g	0.0018						
		1,4-dioxane	mL	60	1440	80 °C, N ₂				
2.2	Extraction	H ₂ O	mL	30						
		Dichloromethane	mL	100						
2.3	Rotary evaporation	Anhydrous Na ₂ SO ₄	g	3						
2.4	Purification	Hexane: Ethyl acetate	L	1L:1L				Column Chromatography	0.6	
3. Synthesis of 3-(2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)methylthiophene (c) C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ S										
3.1	Stirring	<u>3-methanol</u>	g	3				benzaldehyde		
		1-(2-Bromoethoxy)-2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethane	g	7.2						
		tertbutylammoniumbromide (TBAB)	mg	300						

	Water	g	4.5		
	DMSO	mL	5		
	Potassium hydroxide	g	3.4	1440	
3.2 Quenching	Water	mL	100		
Extraction	Ether	mL	5mL		
3.3 Washing	Water	mL	30 MI		
3.4 Drying	anhydrous MgSO4	g	3		
3.5 Purification	Mixture of 7:3 Hexane:Ethyl acetate	L	1L:0.3L		Column chromatography 0.71
4. 2,5-dibromo- 3-(2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)methylthiophene (d) C12H18Br2O4S -M1					
4.1 Stirring	Product (c)	g	2.3		Dry one-necked round bottom flask
	Tetrahydrofuran (THF)	mL	100		
	N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS)	g	4.6	30 0 °C	
4.2 Reaction				60 0 °C	Left in RT overnight
4.3 Filtration and washing	Hexane	mL	10 mL		
4.4 Drying	Magnesium sulfate	g	4		
4.5 Filtration and evaporation					
4.6 Purification	Hexane:Ethyl acetate mixture 8:2	L	1L:0.2L		Column chromatography 0.8
5. MW-1					
5.1 Stirring	Hydrophobic thiophene (b)	g	0.4		
	Hydrophilic thiophene (d)	g	0.22		
	THF	mL	12		
	Sodium carbonate solution	mL	4	10 RT	2 M
5.2 Reflux	Palladium catalyst	mg	5	1440 75 °C	
5.3 Quenching	Water	mL	50		
5.4 Extraction	Dichloromethane	mL	50		
5.5 Drying	Anhydrous MgSO4	g	3		
5.6 Rotary evaporation					

5.7 Purification

Hexane:Ethyl acetate

L 1L:0.2L

Column
chromatography

0.5

Table S2. Life cycle inventory (LCI) for P3HT-block-P3TEGT and P3HT-ran-P3TEGT

Synthesis step	Unit operation	Chemicals	Unit	Amount	Time [min]	Condition	Energy [kWh]	Device	Yield	Other
3. Synthesis of 3-(2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)methylthiophene (c) C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ S										
3.1	Stirring	3-methanol	g	3		benzaldehyde				
		1-(2-Bromoethoxy)-2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethane	g	7.2						
		tertbutylammoniumbromide (TBAB)	mg	300						
		Water	g	4.5						
		DMSO	m							
		Potassium hydroxide	L	5						
			g	3.4	1440					
3.2	Quenching	Water	m							
			L	100 (Total)						
	Extraction	Ether	m							
			L	5mL						
3.3	Washing	Water	m							
			L	30 Ml						
3.4	Drying	anhydrous MgSO ₄	g	3						
3.5	Purification	Mixture of 7:3 Hexane:Ethyl acetate	L	1L:0.3L				Column chromatography	0.7	1
4. 2,5-dibromo- 3-(2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)methylthiophene (d) C ₁₂ H ₁₈ Br ₂ O ₄ S -M1										
4.1	Stirring	Product (c)	g	2.3				Dry one-necked round bottom flask		
		Tetrahydrofuran (THF)	m							
		N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS)	L	100						
			g	4.6	30	0 °C				
4.2	Reaction				60	0 °C		Left in RT overnight		
	Filtration and washing	Hexane	m							
4.3			L	10 mL						
4.4	Drying	Magnesium sulfate	g	4						
4.5	Filtration and evaporation									
4.6	Purification	Hexane:Ethyl acetate mixture 8:2	L	1L:0.2L				Column chromatography	0.8	

5. General procedure for MW-3 P3HT-block-P3TEGT						
5.1 Drying	M3 2-bromo-3-hexyl-5-iodothiophene	g	0.558	10	50 °C	
	M1 (chemical d)	g	0.21	10	50 °C	
5.2 Mixing	THF	g	0.89	15	0	
	Isopropylmagnesium chloride (iPrMgCl)	g	0.22	60	0	2 M
5.2 Mixing	NiCl ₂ (dppp) (C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ NiP ₂), 1,3-bis(diphenylphosphino)propane]-nickel(II) dichloride	mg	18	60	RT	
5.3 Quenching	Methanol	m				
		L	200	720	RT	
5.4 Purification	Methanol, Acetone, Hexane, Chloroform	m	600,			0.5
		m	300,300,30			
		L	0	5760	RT	4
6. General procedure for MW-4 P3HT-ran-P3TEGT						
5.1 Drying	M3	g	0.58	10	50 °C	
	M1	g	0.62	10	50 °C	
5.2 Mixing	THF	g	0.684	15	0	
	Isopropylmagnesium chloride	g	0.176	60	0	2 M
5.2 Mixing	NiCl ₂ (dppp) (C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ NiP ₂)	mg	48	60	RT	
5.3 Quenching	Methanol	m				
		L	200	720	RT	
5.4 Purification	Methanol, Acetone, Hexane, Chloroform	m	600,			0.5
		m	300,300,30			
		L	0	5760	RT	2

